

THE IMPORTANCE OF LITERATURE

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Annotatsiya

Maqolaning maqsadi adabiyotning inson hayotidagi rolini o'rganishdir. Maqolada adabiyotning ahamiyati o'rganilib, bu boradagi ba'zi muhim faktlar va mashhur odamlarning fikrlari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyatni o'rganish, zarur kompetensiyalar, she'riyat qadriyati, chag'atoy adabiyoti.

Аннотация

Цель статьи заключается в изучении роли литературы в жизни человека. В статье рассматривается значение литературы и представлены некоторые важные факты и мнения известных людей.

Ключевые слова: культура обучения, необходимые компетенции, ценность поэзии, чагатайская литература.

Annotation

The aim of the article is to explore the role of literature in human's life. The article investigates the importance of literature and provides some essential facts and the opinions of popular people about this issue.

Key words: learning culture, necessary competencies, value of poetry, Chagatai literature.

Why do we need literature? Why do we study this subject at school or higher education? What is the impact of literature on our life? Well, this types of questions are always quite interesting to answer. First of all, no doubt, the role of literature in our lives can't be overestimated. The amazing virtues provided by literature are uncountable, and it allows to imagine unimaginable. Some of the literary works produced in English are really impressive and have wide importance in our lives. In a narrow context, literature includes works in such directions as prose, fiction, drama, action, romance, and poetry. In recent years, the term literature has broadened and now includes oral literature which can be transcribed as well. Literature may have two key purposes: 1. Entertaining 2. Educational.

Reading a book just for pleasure is entertaining. But when you read a book to learn some interesting and useful information, then it is considered educational purpose. Literature allows the reader to escape the buzzing streets and be lost in mysterious worlds for some period of time. It mounts creative thoughts in the reader. It won't be an exaggeration to say that literature aids in breathing peace into modern society. It serves as a magnifying glass for peeking into the views of other people. Literature diverts us from the routine of our daily lives. For example the American academic C.S.Lewis said that "Literature adds to reality, it does not simply describe it. It enriched the necessary competencies that daily life requires and provides, and in this respect, it irrigates the desert that our lives have already become".

Apart from this Literature enriches the language, helps to develop and discover good skills and words, reveal new personal characteristics, sense the problems in society through a critical view, explore texts from a new perspective, learn about culture, understand the value of poetry, gain the literary skills of classics, and develop good qualities. Literature allows a person to step back in time and learn about life on Earth from the ones who lived before us. One can get a better understanding of culture through literature, and become more informed about the ways the history is recorded.

In addition, literature helps to develop vital analytical and judgmental skills. A well-read person is more capable to find topics for discussion, make connections, and unravel hidden symbols of this world. Accordingly, a regular reader will glide in the river of words to locate the actual motive and detail of each sentence. It enables us to think beyond our boundaries. In short, literature expands the horizons of our wisdom. Learning English literature opens up a world of inspiration and creativity, while also developing skills that are essential for today's global environment. English Literature studies give an opportunity to discover how literature makes sense of the world through stories, poems, novels and plays. English literature is a component part of the world literature.

English literature is a rich literature. It includes masterpieces in many forms, particularly a novel; a short story, an epic and lyric poetry, an essay, literary criticism, and drama. English literature is also one of the oldest national literatures in the world. The masters of English literature from the turn of the XIV century to the present rank among the world's greatest literary figures. Such names as Geoffrey Chaucer, William Shakespeare, Christopher Marlowe, Daniel Defoe, Jonathan Swift, George Gordon Byron, Charles Dickens, Bernard Shaw, John Galsworthy and many others are famous all over the world. Their manner of writing has influenced a great number of writers, poets and playwrights from other countries.

National literature is the reflection of the history and national peculiarities of people. Each national literature has much in common with the world literary progress, but at the same time has its own specific features as well. One of the characteristic features of the English authors is that they have always been deeply interested in political and social environment of their time. They are parts of the real world, which dramatically influences what and how they write. What takes place in the writer's study is crucial, but it also emphasizes the importance of what takes place in the larger world.

However, Uzbek literature, the body of written works produced by the Uzbek people of Central Asia, most of whom live in. Although its roots stretch as far back as the 9th century, modern Uzbek literature traces its origins in large part to Chagatai literature, a body of works written in the Turkic literary language of Chagatai. The earliest works of Chagatai literature date from the 14th century but remain easily accessible to readers of the modern Uzbek language. Modern Uzbek has today assumed the role once held by Chagatai, which all but vanished by the early 20th century, of being the reference language for Turkic historical and literary works in Central Asia. Uzbekistan, with smaller populations in Afghanistan, Tajikistan, and Kyrgyzstan.

The well-known, popular Uzbek writer Abdulhamid Sulaymon o'g'li Cho'lpon said that, the nation lives until its literature is alive. This sentence has a deep meaning. Literature is also a mean for mitigate the restlessness faced by humans in modern bustling world.

History plays a crucial role in forging literature. Every novel, poem, story we have, was influenced by political or cultural history. Literature helps to develop vital analytical and judgement skills. Also Literature is important for the basics of life itself. It emphasizes many topics, from human tragedies to tales about the search for love. Physically written words come alive in the imagination, making it possible to comprehend the complexity of the text.

The words of American author, journalist, and commentator Anna Quinlen perfectly sum up the thought provided above: "Books are the plane, and the train, and the road. They are the destination and the journey. They are home." So, read more books, because they open new doors in our lives, broaden our outlook, and make us understand the world better. Many of them describe real world and real situations directly, while others do it through a figurative sense. And there is no doubt that Literature is crucial element for in our lives.

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